

A Review Paper on Barshi Optical's Optical's Android Application

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Abstract:- The "optic operation" design is a comprehensive digital result designed to streamline and manage information for optic shops. This operation offers a stoner-friendly platform to efficiently handle force operation, client records, tradition shadowing. By employing the power of technology, the design aims to enhance functional effectiveness and client experience within optic stores, eventually revolutionizing the way optic businesses operate and serve their clientele.

Keywords:- Comprehensive; revolutionizing; Category; Product; Order; Bill.

I. INTRODUCTION

One of the main forces behind frugal living in every nation is business, and since the turn of the 20th century, all businesses have looked to technology to increase their rates and business opportunities. Thus, the rationale behind the creation of this system is comparable. This system was created specifically for the optical industry, and it will be implemented in every optical company retail location. Optic Shop Operation is the name of the system (OSA). The system is designed to make operations considerably more systematic, safe, and efficient. The modules that make up OSA include fiscal operation, shop operation, and login.

Table 1 describes the capabilities of the modules. productivity of the business.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Lenskart

One of the top online retailers in India, Lenskart offers contact lenses, sunglasses, and other eyewear in addition to specs. The business has been promoting its name and goods using brightly coloured advertising techniques. Our goal in this design is to investigate how Lenskart's advertising affects sales and brand awareness. Lenskart is an impressive Indian eyewear-commerce company that was innovated in 2010. The company's main office is in Faridabad, India, and it has a huge physical retail network in numerous Indian cities. Millions of visitors in India now trust Lenskart as a brand.

Lenskart is renowned for its creative approach to the marketing of eyewear. Allowing customers to try on frames before making a purchase, the company was among the first in India to promote the concept of "Try Before You Buy". Lenskart employs cutting-edge technology to provide precise and customised purchasing experiences for its customers. Examples of these features include virtual frame recommendations and 3D pass-on. Lenskart offers a vast

physical retail network, with over 700 locations spread across 175 Indian metropolises, in addition to its online presence. The business has opened outlets in Singapore and the Middle East as part of its global expansion. For its creative approach to merchandising, Lenskart has received numerous honours and recognitions. In 2020, it was crowned the "Most respected Retailer of the Time". [1].

B. Vision Glasses Optical Store in Surabaya

Vision spectacles is a Surabaya- grounded eyewear shop dealing high- quality, affordable spectacles, lenses, and eyewear accessories. This thesis intends to bandy the being directorial issue in Vision spectacles, videlicet work performance. This exploration employs proposition of constraints and the proposition of work procedure. After collecting the data from the proprietor and workers of Vision spectacles, the pen discovers that Vision spectacles needs to apply a work procedure which contains rules or guidelines similar as the policy, client- service ethics, and division instructions for the workers and as a guideline for the company to punish the workers or deal with internal conflict.[2]

C. WarbyParker

This business was initially designed to allow drug users to select and purchase connections, sunglasses, and eyeglasses. However, the creators have since included a Virtual Try-On AI-driven feature. It shows you how a particular model of eyewear will appear on your face in real time using augmented reality. Furthermore, unlike with a print, you won't see the reflection in just one aircraft. It keeps your specs in place as though you were actually wearing them, allowing you to move your head up, down, or side to side. To get started, open the Warby Parker app and select the desired model. If the model is available, you will see an announcement stating that you can try it on almost immediately. Nevertheless, if a particular model appeals to you, click the Home Try-On button. The business will send you up to five pairs for a real-world try-on. Otherwise, you can purchase it straight from the app if you've configured the precise model..[3]

D. Glasses Camera

This app is excellent for selecting the ideal brace of glasses from a variety of models to improve vision. You can see trendy sunglasses & eyeglasses in various styles, as well as eyewear that is the same colour but in different shapes. If all you want to do is snap a photo of yourself trying on glasses, the app lets you store photos and share them on social media.

It's also helpful if you wish to store multiple pictures of various pairs of eyeglasses so you can later compare them and select the most fashionable pair. This app for passing on eyeglasses has vibrant tools for rotating, flipping, and zooming in on filmland. In addition to crisp photos, the app provides goods with colour. Using this filters app, you can adjust sharpness, achromatism, brilliance, and discrepancy to enhance your filmland. What's more, you can choose the matching haircut to look swish in prints.[3]

E. Glass On

With Glass On, stoners can try on multiple frame types in real time based on shape and type. The integrated augmented reality technology in this virtual pass on specs app gives you a lifelike experience. You can find the perfect pair of stylish glasses for your face shape by trying on different models and customising them if needed. Additionally, you can snap a photo with the requested specifications and share it on the most popular social media platforms. Just grant access to your camera to begin; there is no registration or payment required. The inventors put up a website where they provide innovations to any other business looking to integrate this technology into its operations. They run a store online. [3]

F. Ideofit

Decision With the help of the pass-on eyewear app Ideofit, you can try on various shaped eyewear in the comfort of your own home.

You are welcome to try on the accessory, select the stylish bone that suits you best, and purchase it from the store. The software is able to identify eyewear that complements your face type. Simply place the phone in front of you and proceed without covering your face. The process provides you with a variety of colourful face frames from which to select the one that best suits your tastes.

After positioning the smartphone and spectacles correctly, snap a photo. Once completed, you can give it to your musketeers to find out what they think of a particular style of eyewear. You can experiment with any brace that the app offers and use various filters. If you have your eye on a particular model, though, you can place an order by going to Amazon. Additionally, it makes it possible for you to locate eyewear from well-known labels like Versace, Gucci, and Prada. Because AR technology is mandated, the app assists you in selecting the appropriate eyewear based on your face. Ideofit sticks out thanks to its user-friendly interface and quick store access. [3]

III. OBJECTIVE

- Develop an intuitive optic operation to efficiently manage and organize force, deals, and client information for an optic store..
- Enhance client experience by furnishing a stoner-friendly interface for opting and copping eyewear products, while maintaining accurate record.
- Streamline executive tasks through automated appointment scheduling and order processing, optimizing functional effectiveness and reducing homemade crimes.
- Facilitate data- driven decision- making by generating perceptive reports on deals trends, popular products, and client preferences, abetting the optic shop's growth and success.

IV. METHODOLOGY

A. DFD Level 2

Fig. 1: Example of a figure caption.(figure caption)

B. Explanation

The owner is directly connected with admin login, customer details, shopping cart and bill generation.

The product includes the customer database for storing customer details such as customer name, address, age, mobile no. and customer vision number.

V. FUTURE SCOPE

The operation helps in maintaining the record of the guests vision number and the type of spectacles and lenses they use. Having formerly turned profitable and attained the number one position in the ingrained eyewear order, the nine-time-old start up is looking to make on the earnings with a focus on league 2 and league 3 metropolises.

A. Figures and Tables

Table 1: Modules and function list

Module	Function
Adminlogin	• Login to the system
Master	• Use to store record of different things.
Financial Management	• Manage the financial of the company • Holding every branch financial account to keep record on their earning

a. Sample of a Table footnote.(*Tablefootnote*)

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